

Novafert

Novafert

D2.5 – Results of social LCA

<i>Author(s):</i>	<i>Marzena Smol, Paulina Marcinek, Mateusz Skalny - MEERI PAS Jorge Senan Salinas, Miguel Montero Alonso, Carmen Capdevila Murillo - BETA Technological Centre (UVic-UCC)</i>
<i>Version:</i>	<i>Final version</i>
<i>Quality review:</i>	<i>Nimisha Edayilam - UGent Karetta Vikki – LUKE Kari Ylivainio - LUKE</i>
<i>Date:</i>	<i>30/04/2025</i>
<i>Dissemination level:</i>	<i>Public (PU)</i>
<i>Grant Agreement N°:</i>	<i>101060835</i>
<i>Starting Date:</i>	<i>01-09-2022</i>
<i>Duration:</i>	<i>36 months</i>
<i>Coordinator:</i>	<i>Prof. Erik Meers, Ghent University</i>
<i>Contact details:</i>	<i>erik.meers@ugent.be</i>

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
List of Tables.....	3
List of Figures	4
Abbreviations	4
Executive Summary.....	5
1 S-LCA Methodology.....	7
1.1 Theoretical foundations of S-LCA.....	7
1.2 UNEP Guidelines in the context of S-LCA.....	8
1.3 Principles and approaches used in S-LCA.....	9
2 Methods.....	10
2.1 Goal and scope.....	10
2.2 System boundaries.....	10
2.3 Data acquisition	11
3 S-LCA for analysis bio-based fertilisers (BBFs)	11
3.1 BBF 1.....	11
3.1.1 Company profile	11
3.1.2 S-LCA Assessment and Interpretation.....	12
3.2 BBF 2.....	14
3.2.1 Company profile	14
3.2.2 S-LCA Assessment and Interpretation.....	14
3.3 BBF 3.....	16
3.3.1 Company profile	16
3.3.2 S-LCA Assessment and Interpretation.....	16
3.4 BBF 4.....	18
3.4.1 Company profile	18
3.4.2 S-LCA Assessment and Interpretation.....	19
4 PSILCA database	20
4.1 General information about PSILCA.....	20
4.2 Goal and scope.....	22
4.3 Findings obtained using the PSILCA database.....	23

5	Discussion and feedback on all examined BBFs	29
5.1	Categories and subcategories of social impacts	29
5.2	Stakeholder analysis	32
5.2.1.	Main stakeholder groups.....	32
5.2.2.	Main stakeholder groups interests and expectations.....	33
5.2.3.	Impact of the BBFs product system on stakeholders	35
5.3	Discussion on PSILCA findings	36
5.4	Summary of key findings.....	36
5.5	Recommendations	37
5.6	Future challenges	38
	References.....	40
	Annex 1: Survey template used for data collection.....	41

List of Tables

Table 1.	Scope, impact types and object of S-LCA.....	7
Table 2.	Key principles applied in S-LCA for BBFs.....	9
Table 3.	Social impact categories by Medium Risk Hours per tonne of the 13 BBFs in Spain	23
Table 4.	Social impact categories by Medium Risk Hours per tonne of the 13 BBFs in Belgium	24
Table 5.	Social impact categories by Medium Risk Hours per tonne of the 13 BBFs in Sweden	26
Table 6.	Social impact categories by Medium Risk Hours per tonne of the 13 BBFs in Italy ...	27
Table 7.	Social impact categories by Medium Risk Hours per tonne of the 13 BBFs in Poland	28
Table 8.	Characteristics of stakeholder groups.....	33
Table 9.	Stakeholder impact analysis of BBFs and distribution	35

List of Figures

Figure 1. System boundaries for BBFs.....	10
Figure 2. Accident monitoring system (BBF 2).....	17

Abbreviations

BBFs – bio-based fertilisers
BE – Belgium
CE – Circular Economy
E-LCA – Environmental Life Cycle Analysis
ES – Spain
EU – European Union
IT – Italy
LCA – Life Cycle Analysis
LCC – Life Cycle Cost
PL - Poland
SE- Sweden
S-LCA - Social Life Cycle Assessment
SDGs - Sustainable Development Goals
UNEP - United Nations Environment Programme

Executive Summary

The purpose of this report is to conduct a Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) of bio-based fertilisers (BBFs) investigated under the Novafert project. BBFs include – soil improvers or alternative fertilisers made from bio-waste materials intended for use in agriculture. The analysis aims to identify social and sociological aspects associated with the production, distribution, and use of these products, covering potential positive and negative impacts on stakeholders throughout its life cycle. This report serves as a complement to environmental LCA and cost analysis (LCC), supporting the objectives of sustainable development and the goals of the European Green Deal.

To achieve these objectives, the report focuses on aspects relevant to key stakeholders and social indicators that impact the quality of life in local communities and workplace safety. The analysis also includes identifying opportunities to support the local economy through the production and distribution of BBFs. The assessment scope encompasses the entire life cycle of four BBFs, from the acquisition of secondary raw materials through production and distribution processes to their use and potential effects on soil and local communities. The analysis covers the following topics for each BBFs:

- five main stakeholder groups: employees, consumers, local communities, society and entities within the value chain,
- key social indicators: including job creation, impacts on public health and local development,
- collection of qualitative data following UNEP guidelines,
- social impact assessment of 13 BBFs using PSILCA database.

The system boundaries include both production at the processing facility and the distribution of the product to the end-user. The report also examines the potential benefits and risks associated with the product's use in the context of its impact on local communities. The report incorporates both specific data for the chochen BBFs and general data for the fertilisers. sector. This approach ensures an accurate assessment of social impact and allows for the formulation of conclusions and recommendations for the further development of the products.

The findings confirm that BBFs, derived from organic waste materials, can offer considerable social and environmental benefits. These benefits are especially evident in:

- job creation in local communities and rural regions,
- improved working conditions and safety protocols in most production sites,
- promotion of circular economy (CE) practices through waste valorisation,
- environmental and public health improvements due to reduced chemical fertiliser use.

The findings confirm that BBFs, derived from organic waste materials, can offer considerable social and environmental benefits. These benefits are especially evident in job creation in local communities and rural regions, improved working conditions and safety protocols in most production sites, promotion of CE practices through waste valorisation, and environmental and public health improvements due to reduced chemical fertiliser use. However, the analysis also reveals areas where improvement is necessary. These include more structured stakeholder engagement, greater transparency in customer and community relations, limited gender representation in the workforce, insufficient monitoring of social responsibility along the supply chain, and the fact that social impacts are highly dependent on the geographic context where production takes place.

In light of the findings, several recommendations are proposed to strengthen the social sustainability of BBF value chains. It is advised to promote inclusive and equitable working environments, including developing formal policies to support workplace diversity, closing gender pay gaps, and encouraging the participation of underrepresented groups. It is also recommended to strengthen occupational health and safety practices through ongoing employee training, internal audits, and continuous improvement protocols. Furthermore, companies should enhance community engagement and conduct formal assessments of their social and environmental impacts, implement systematic customer satisfaction monitoring tools, develop supplier evaluation standards for social responsibility, and improve transparency and stakeholder communication through regular reporting.

Looking ahead, BBF producers must be prepared to address several future challenges. These include adapting to an evolving regulatory landscape concerning environmental protection and waste-derived fertilisers, maintaining competitiveness through innovation and demonstrating economic value, building public trust by improving communication and transparency, and aligning operations with global sustainability goals such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Collaboration with stakeholders and continuous improvement across the entire supply chain will be key to ensuring the long-term success and social acceptance of BBFs.

1 S-LCA Methodology

1.1 Theoretical foundations of S-LCA

Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) is a method for evaluating social and sociological impacts associated with a product’s life cycle (Table 1). Influenced by the ISO 14040 standard (ISO 14040 2006) for Environmental Life Cycle Assessment (E-LCA), it analyses all stages of a product's life cycle - from raw material extraction, production and distribution to use and end-of-life disposal or recycling (Jørgensen et al. 2008).

Table 1. Scope, impact types and object of S-LCA (UNEP 2020)

System scope	Impact types	Object of study
<p>Entire life cycle of products and services — covering all stages from resource extraction, through production and use, to final disposal or recycling (cradle-to-grave approach)</p> <p>Product supply chain (cradle-to-gate; exclude use phase and end-of-life).</p> <p>Specific stages of the life cycle — focusing on selected segments such as production or distribution only (gate-to-gate or gate-to-grave).</p>	<p>Actual or potential impacts on social and socio-economic conditions, varying according to the context of application.</p>	<p>Product or services.</p>

The key premise of S-LCA is the identification and evaluation of potential social impacts related to stakeholders such as workers, local communities, consumers, suppliers and other groups (UNEP/SETAC 2009). S-LCA enables a better understanding of how the product’s life cycle affects social aspects such as working conditions, local development, social equity and public health (Bouillass, Blanc, and Perez-Lopez 2021).

Two main approaches are considered in S-LCA. First, the Reference Scale method based on analysing social performance or social risks of a product systems, usually, it is associated to a context-specific analysis of the case studies of a particular project (UNEP 2020). Second, the

Impact Pathway Approach, which is used to predict the consequences of the product systems, highlighting the potential social impacts of the production across the value-chain. In the context of NOVAFERT project, two approaches are combined to better capture the social impacts at different levels of assessment. On one hand, the approach at company level enables the assessment of social impacts of the organisation, as social impacts are mostly dependent of organisational behaviour and not only production processes (ISO 14040 2006). On the other hand, the PSILCA assessment shows the impacts throughout the supply chain and by functional unit, which is more in line with the logic of life cycle thinking and allows for comparison (Ciroth and Eisfeldt 2015). Since a company can produce multiple BBFs, it is also important to identify differences in social impacts based on the specific type of product.

The theoretical foundations of S-LCA are closely tied to the concept of sustainable development, which integrates economic, environmental, and social aspects. In the context of BBFs, particular emphasis is placed on (UNEP 2020):

- impact on the quality of life for local communities,
- job creation in the region,
- improvement of soil health and food security.

1.2 UNEP Guidelines in the context of S-LCA

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) guidelines serve as a critical document for implementing S-LCA in sustainability analyses. UNEP's publication, "Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations," (UNEP/SETAC 2009) defines the methodological framework and principles for conducting S-LCA.

The main elements of UNEP guidelines include (Figure 1):

1. Stakeholder-oriented approach

The analysis should consider impacts on key stakeholder groups, such as workers, local communities, consumers, suppliers and policymakers.

2. System boundaries

The UNEP guidelines recommend a comprehensive approach, covering both direct processes related to the product and indirect impacts across the supply chain.

3. Categories of social impacts

The guidelines define standard categories, such as human rights, working conditions, health and safety, local development, access to resources, and social well-being.

4. Data quality and sources

UNEP emphasizes the importance of using reliable and representative data, both quantitative and qualitative, to enable a thorough assessment of social impacts.

1.3 Principles and approaches used in S-LCA

Conducting an S-LCA analysis requires the application of specific principles and approaches to ensure consistent and credible results (Table 2). For the analysis of BBFs, the following approaches were applied:

1. Stakeholder-based approach

The analysis focuses on identifying stakeholder groups and their needs and expectations. For BBFs, key groups include farmers, plant workers, local communities, and suppliers.

2. Life cycle approach

The assessment covers all stages of the product's life cycle—from the processing of secondary raw materials, through production and distribution, to its use by farmers and its final impact on soil.

3. Use of social indicators

S-LCA uses social indicators, which are measurable parameters that assess aspects such as workplace safety, public health, the number of jobs created, or support for the local economy.

4. Transparency and stakeholder participation

Engaging stakeholders in the assessment process is essential to increase the credibility and acceptance of the analysis results.

5. Data quality assessment

The data quality used in the analysis is assessed based on criteria such as completeness, consistency, reliability and timeliness.

Table 2. Key principles applied in S-LCA for BBFs (UNEP/SETAC 2009; UNEP 2020)

Principles	Description
Stakeholder Orientation	Consideration of impacts on key stakeholder groups
Life Cycle Approach	Analysis covers all stages of the product's life cycle
Use of Social Indicators	Use of measurable parameters for evaluating social impacts
Transparency	Ensuring data access and involving stakeholders in the analysis process
Data Quality	Verification and assessment of the completeness and reliability of the data used

2 Methods

2.1 Goal and scope

The primary objective of the study is to establish a comprehensive foundation for conducting a Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) of BBFs. This will be pursued through an in-depth examination of the social dimensions associated with both the production processes and the market implementation of BBFs. To achieve this goal, the study will employ a survey-based research methodology, targeting companies actively engaged in the production of BBFs. Through the systematic collection and analysis of data from these entities, the research aims to generate valuable insights into the social impacts, challenges, and opportunities linked to the development and diffusion of BBFs within the market.

Second, a specific S-LCA for the 13 BBFs¹ using PSILCA database is performed to analyse social impacts along the life cycle of them (see section 4). The BBFs assessed refer to those assessed in Deliverable 2.3, following the same identification code, and correspond to those produced by the companies firstly analysed.

2.2 System boundaries

The S-LCA system boundaries for BBFs encompass for the first analysis all significant stages of the product's life cycle, from raw material extraction through production, distribution, and usage, to final disposal. For the PSILCA analysis, systems boundaries are limited to the same as in the LCC and LCA analysis, excluding the final product stage, from cradle-to-gate.

The analysis focuses on the following elements:

- upstream processes / raw material acquisition: covering the supply of sewage sludge and additional materials,
- production processes: all operations carried out at the production facility (e.g. drying, stabilisation, addition of enrichers, granulation, and packaging),
- distribution and sales: logistics related to delivering the product to end users,
- usage: methods of applying the product and its impact on soil quality (actions taken by farmers and other user groups),
- end-of-life phase: possibilities for reuse or disposal of the product (options for using residuals of BBFs in the soil).

Figure 1. System boundaries for BBFs

¹ Please refer to Deliverable 2.3 - Section 4 for specific information on the BBFs analysed.

Moreover, analysis considers the following stakeholders:

- workers (company staff, production workers),
- local communities (impact of production and product use),
- consumers (farmers, landscapers),
- government and regulatory bodies (compliance oversight).

2.3 Data acquisition

The questionnaire was designed and sent to four case studies in the bioeconomy sector to obtain data on the social aspects of BBFs' production. The questionnaire involved questions related to:

- employment - understanding the workforce dynamics and job creation associated with BBF production,
- working conditions - assessing the environment in which employees operate and the overall workplace safety,
- training and development - evaluating the opportunities provided for skill enhancement and professional growth,
- safety protocols - investigating the measures in place to ensure the safety of workers and consumers,
- product composition - analyzing the ingredients and materials used in BBFs and their implications for health and sustainability,
- customer perceptions - gathering insights on how consumers view and value BBFs in the market,
- community impact - exploring the effects of BBF production on local communities and their economies,
- regulatory compliance - reviewing adherence to laws and regulations governing the production and sale of BBFs.

The obtained data were analyzed to define social impacts and relationships with stakeholders and throughout all product life cycles.

3 S-LCA for analysis bio-based fertilisers (BBFs)

3.1 BBF 1

3.1.1 Company profile

BBF 1 is an innovative soil improver developed from stabilized sewage sludges in Poland. Its primary purpose is to enrich soil with nutrients, improve its structure, and enhance water retention. The product is particularly beneficial in agricultural areas with poor soils, where traditional chemical fertilisers may be less effective or harmful to the environment.

Properties of BBF 1 indicated by producer:

- high organic matter content: thanks to the sewage sludge base, the product contains a rich set of macro- and micronutrients,
- safety in use: the stabilization process eliminates pathogens and reduces heavy metal content to levels acceptable under EU standards,
- eco-friendliness: Utilizing sewage sludge as a raw material reduces the need for chemical soil improvement agents.

Applications of BBF 1 indicated by producer:

- agriculture: enriching soil in agricultural operations,
- reclamation of degraded areas: improving soil structure in industrial regions,
- urban greenery: use in parks and green spaces in cities.

The production process of BBF 1 involves:

- **collection and preparation** — the facility processes approximately 17 million cubic meters of sewage annually, producing around 20 000 tons of sludge. This sludge undergoes thorough analysis to determine its suitability for further processing,
- **stabilization** — The sludge is stabilized by drying at 130°C. This step effectively reduces pathogens and odors, ensuring safety for agricultural applications,
- **enrichment** — Dried sludge is enhanced with microbiological preparations and natural additives. These enrichments improve the product's soil-forming qualities, making it versatile for different agricultural uses,
- **granulation and packaging** — the processed sludge is formed into granules or similar products to facilitate storage and transport. It is packaged in various sizes to cater to consumer demand,
- **production scale and impact** — the facility produced approximately 1 400 tons of BBF 1 in 2022, scaling production to match growing demand. The product serves as a cost-effective and sustainable alternative to conventional fertilisers, gaining popularity among farmers due to rising fertiliser prices in Poland.

3.1.2 S-LCA Assessment and Interpretation

Working conditions

The company has its own policy related to the contract conditions for employees.

The company operates a two-shift system: Monday through Friday, the first shift is 6:45-14:45, and the second shift is 14:45–22:25.

The company offers various types of training for its employees depending on their current needs.

Occupational health and safety

Depending on the role, several regulations related to workplace safety are followed in the company. Moreover, an accident monitoring system exists, but to this day, no accidents have been noted.

Respect for workers' rights

The company complies with local and international labor regulations, including those prohibiting forced labor and child labor. However, the company does not have a direct policy on Equal treatment and non-discrimination in the workplace.

User health and safety

The company carries out all required tests concerning health and safety, as well as the composition and characteristics of BBF1. Moreover, the company delivers information related to the potential dangers of product usage.

Customer satisfaction

The company does not conduct the analysis of client satisfaction.

Standards for cooperation with suppliers

In the case of BBF 1, there are no external suppliers. The production process requires only internal raw materials generated during company operations.

Monitoring of supplier social responsibility

No audits are conducted.

Impact on the local community

The use of natural fertilisers in agriculture/forestry/horticulture, waste, without negative side effects.

Social commitment

The company actively participates in local community initiatives. However, it has not yet undertaken any actions specifically aimed at disseminating knowledge related to sustainability and environmental protection.

Compliance with government regulations

The company complies with all local, national and international regulations regarding waste management and environmental protection. It holds all the required licenses and certifications for the production and sale of the soil improver.

3.2 BBF 2

3.2.1 Company profile

The company repurposes various industrial side streams—such as mixed sludge from pulp and paper mills—into fertilisers, soil amendments and raw materials for industrial applications. Its end users include farmers and industrial customers. The main markets the company targets are agriculture (Finland and Sweden) and industrial uses of byproducts (Finland).

The company operations regarding the implementation of BBF 2 include:

- administrative tasks – 0.5 Pearson involved,
- operational tasks (coordinating production, quality control, logistics) – 1 Pearson involved,
- sales – 1 Pearson involved,
- production (by contractors) – 1 Pearson involved,
- transportation (by contractors) –1 Pearson involved,
- product application (by contractors) – 0.5 Pearson involved.

3.2.2 S-LCA Assessment and Interpretation

Working conditions

The company employs 28 people, of whom 39% are women and one is part-time. The average salary of a company employee is 4600 €/month (4100 €/month for a woman and 5100 €/month for a man). The typical weekly working time in the company is 37,5 h/week, and overtime is not a typical practice.

The company provides targeted training programs for its employees, including practical workshops, online courses, webinars, meetings with industry experts, and collaborative learning opportunities. It also promotes team initiative by encouraging individuals to propose learning paths that support their personal growth and respond to current market challenges. Moreover, the company indicated that 3.6% of its costs are related to employee benefits (e.g., health care, training).

Occupational health and safety

Company operations are aligned with ISO 9001(ISO 9001 2015). Clear processes, defined responsibilities, and risk-based thinking promote workplace safety. The company implements an accident reporting and monitoring system (according to ISO 9001) and an anonymous whistleblowing system. To this day, no accidents have been noted during company operations.

Respect for workers' rights

A continuous dialogue between the parties takes place to enable proper relations between

the company and its employees. However, there is no set framework for facilitating that. The company's code of conduct serves as a set of guidelines and principles that outline the expected ethical behavior, values, and standards for individuals within an organisation. The employees' satisfaction is evaluated thrice yearly by conducting a satisfaction survey.

User health and safety

The company produces BBFs originating from waste streams (mainly bioactive). Therefore, it conducts safety studies according to Finnish fertiliser legislation. The company also provides a product information sheet and specific instructions for use.

Customer satisfaction

To evaluate customer satisfaction and monitor feedback, the company conducts a yearly survey of both industries providing the side streams and end users. To this day, the company has noted only one formal complaint.

Standards for cooperation with suppliers

As the company's main aim is to produce BBFs from waste material streams, only suppliers providing materials available for recycling are considered. Suppliers are evaluated according to the company's code of conduct for contractors.

Monitoring of supplier social responsibility

The company does not audit the social practices of its suppliers, but it conducts general audits of contractors cooperating with the company.

Impact on the local community

The company has not yet assessed the social impact of the production and implementation of BBFs, but the expected impacts include:

- reduced side stream handling costs, leading to improved profitability,
- more eco-friendly production, aligning with company values,
- improved soil health, enhancing the resilience of agricultural production and supporting farmer wellbeing,
- contribution to the development of the local economy.

Social commitment

The company does not participate in social and educational programs and initiatives.

Compliance with government regulations

The company's operation complies with national waste legislation, national fertiliser legislation – ISO 14001 (ISO 14001 2015).

3.3 BBF 3

3.3.1 Company profile

The company's core activity is producing fertilisers and soil amendments from biodegradable waste. Its sole target market is the Spanish agricultural sector. To produce and deliver BBFs to clients, the company indicates the following roles for its employees:

- operators – liquid area: 2 – full size,
- operators – solid area: 2 –full size,
- other operators: 2 – full size,
- administrative staff (scale): 3 – full volume,
- quality technician: 1 – full volume.

3.3.2 S-LCA Assessment and Interpretation

Working conditions

The company employs 28 people full-time, of whom 17.86 % are females, and two are employed temporarily (both men). The average salary for men is slightly higher than for women, equaling 2 216 and 2 199 €/month, respectively. The minimum salary in the company is equal to 1 363.5 €/month and is paid to 3.57 % of employees (1 employee).

The standard weekly working time for company employees is 40 hours with no overtime.

The company supports the professional development of its employees through training initiatives tailored to our specific needs. These include a diverse range of opportunities such as hands-on workshops, online courses, webinars, expert sessions, and collaborative learning. We also foster individual initiative by encouraging team members to suggest training paths that match their growth goals and align with market demands.

Occupational health and safety

The company implements multiple procedures improving workplace safety, which include identifying and assessing workplace hazards (Risk Assessment), implementing preventive actions to reduce risks, ensuring the use of required personal protective equipment (PPE) based on job roles, and utilizing visual signage and communication systems to signal potential dangers and emergencies. It also involves training employees in best practices and emergency procedures, as well as conducting routine inspections and maintenance of machinery and equipment to prevent malfunctions and accidents, among other measures. Moreover, an accident monitoring system exists (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Accident monitoring system (BBF 2)

To this day, a total of 4 accidents during the company's operation have been noted.

Respect for workers' rights

To assess and cope with the workers' rights company implements following strategies and actions:

- direct communication with human resources and management,
- regular meetings,
- suggestion box,
- whistleblowing channel,
- internal chat.

The company implements tailored policies to promote equal treatment and prevent discrimination in the workplace, including a protocol for prevention and action against harassment and a code of conduct. Currently, the company plans to implement practices connected to formalizing and sensitizing staff on workplace harassment, sexual harassment, and gender-based harassment.

User health and safety

To assure the safety of the BBFs, the company follows the actual legislation and conducts random sampling to check that they meet microbiological characteristics (Salmonella, E. coli). Moreover, the company's clients are provided with complete information about the composition and properties of the product, including potential hazards.

Customer satisfaction

Company do not assess and monitor the satisfaction of the customers. However, no complaints have been noted to this day.

Standards for cooperation with suppliers

To evaluate suppliers, the company uses the following criteria: quality, price, and environmental (environmental management system, biodegradable, ecolabel, FSC). However, there is no internal policy or regulations connected to this matter.

Impact on the local community

The company has never evaluated the social impacts of its operation, but the expected impacts follow:

- creation of both direct and indirect jobs (e.g., in services, workshops, restaurants) within a rural community,
- stimulation of local economic activity,
- improved access to fertiliser products for nearby agricultural and livestock producers.

The negative expected impact encompasses the intensification of truck passage and odors. The company has already taken action to reduce odor issues.

Social commitment

The company promotes a local soccer team and organises site visits for students from nearby high schools.

Compliance with government regulations

Company operation (the production of BBFs) complies with the CO₂ footprint, ISO 14001 (ISO 14001 2015) and EMAS regulations (European Parliament 2009). Additionally, the company conducts a set of analyses of waste material used for BBFs production.

3.4 BBF 4

3.4.1 Company profile

The company's main aim is to treat livestock manure by anaerobic treatment, which results in the production of biogas, combined with electricity generation and organic fertiliser production. The company treats waste streams generated by the livestock industry (95%) and agriculture (5%), all from Spain.

To sustain its operations, the company undertakes the following activities connected to the processing of bio-based waste materials:

- reception - 10 (in shifts of 2 people) and 2 directions,
- separation - 10 (in shifts of 2 people) and 2 directions,
- dehydration - 10 (in shifts of 2 people) and 2 directions,
- solid fraction drying - 10 (in shifts of 2 people) and 2 directions,
- liquid fraction drying - 10 (in shifts of 2 people) and 2 directions,
- cogeneration - 2 maintenance and 2 steering,

- installation maintenance - 3 maintenance and 2 management,
- environmental management and requirements - 2 address.

3.4.2 S-LCA Assessment and Interpretation

Working conditions

The company employs 17 people full-time (all men). The company's average monthly salary is 2.200€, while the minimum salary is 1 840€, received by 40% of the employees.

For maintenance and management employees, the typical working week is 40 hours.

Operating personnel work in 5-week shift system, with the following considerations:

- 1st week morning 64 hours from Monday to Sunday,
- 2nd week party from Monday to Sunday,
- 3rd week 40h from Monday to Friday,
- 4th Week 64 hours Monday to Sunday,
- 5th week holiday from Monday to Sunday.

Overtimes occur 1-2 times per month only for maintenance and management employees.

The company offers several courses for its employees: training in working at heights, Forklift truck license, Boiler Handling Course, and Electrical training.

Occupational health and safety

The company controls various working safety issues previously identified by the external advisor, which include Fire hazards, sulfuric acid discharge, working at height, working with noise, and heavy material handling. The external occupational risk prevention (ORP) company makes monthly visits to the facility to audit workplace safety.

Respect for workers' rights

Daily supervision of management and monthly supervision of the ORP person assures proper dialogue between management and employees, enabling good execution of workers' rights. Moreover, the company organizes staff meetings to facilitate relations within the organization.

User health and safety

The company complies with current regulations and performs random sampling to verify compliance with microbiological standards (e.g., Salmonella, E. coli).

Customer satisfaction

Currently, customer satisfaction is not measured.

Standards for cooperation with suppliers

The suppliers are only local farms, so they are not evaluated.

Monitoring of supplier social responsibility

The social responsibility of suppliers is also not monitored.

Impact on the local community

Company operations invoke the following social impacts:

- increase in cooperation between local suppliers and companies,
- reduction of the use of chemical fertilisers,
- improvement of organic fertilisation,
- promoting the CE.

Social commitment

The owner of the company is involved in multiple non-profit social entities linked to sports and culture.

Compliance with government regulations

Company operations and products comply with ISO 14001 and the regulations described in the environmental authorization.

4 PSILCA database

4.1 General information about PSILCA

Product Social Impact Life Cycle Assessment database (PSILCA) is a database designed to facilitate the social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) of products. It provides comprehensive information and data on social indicators across different sectors, enabling companies, researchers, and practitioners to evaluate and measure the social impacts of their products or services throughout the supply chain. PSILCA supports decision-making by offering insights into potential risks, opportunities, and areas for improvement in social sustainability.

PSILCA v.3 database on OpenLCA enables to track the social impacts of the products and all their components along their life cycle, considering multiple sources of information and stakeholders. The PSILCA database, developed by GreenDelta and available within the open-source LCA software "openLCA", provides transparent and up-to-date information on social aspects for almost 15,000 industry sectors and commodities and 69 qualitative and

quantitative indicators (Maister et al., 2020). PSILCA is based on EORA, a multi-regional input/output (MRIO) database that includes 189 countries and around 15,000 sectors classified into industries and commodities. EORA is based on economic flows between processes, where inputs/outputs tables reflect the exchange flows occurring in a given economic system during a period. The reference flow in PSILCA is one USD dollar output of value created, and the activity variable is “working hours” (i.e. the total number of hours needed to produce 1 USD). The latest available year in the 2019 release was 2015, which is used as a reference year for EORA in PSILCA (Maister et al. 2020).

Following UNEP/SETAC Guidelines structure, indicators in PSILCA are grouped into into 25 social and socioeconomic subcategories and the four stakeholder categories: workers, local community, society and value-chain actors (UNEP/SETAC 2009). Indicators are quantified in medium-risk hours, which means the hours with an average risk of a particular social issue occurring. Data source for indicators are statistical agencies (e.g. World Bank, International Labour Organisation, World Health Organization or United Nations), private or governmental databases, public records on environmental health and Safety violations, by company or industry and site-specific information from cases studies carried out by GreenDelta (Maister et al. 2020). Indicators are scored using an ordinal negative social risk scale of 6 levels, ranging from no risk to very high risk, and a positive social opportunity scale. The assignment of risk levels to the indicator values is based on international conventions and standards, labour laws and expert opinions (Maister et al. 2020). Each risk levels are assigned by a characterization factor: no risk = 0, very low risk = 0.01, low risk = 0.1, medium risk = 1, high risk = 10, very high risk = 100 and a missing value (no data) equals to low risk. Final impacts are calculated considering the economic flow, activity variable and risk level.

Key Features of PSILCA:

1. Wide sectoral coverage: PSILCA includes data for numerous economic sectors, helping users analyze diverse industries and supply chains.
2. Social indicators: the database contains detailed indicators aligned with the United Nations SDGs and other frameworks, such as worker rights, child labor risks, fair wages, and health and safety conditions.
3. Regional differentiation: social impacts can vary by region; PSILCA provides country-specific or regionally differentiated data for improved assessment accuracy.
4. Quantitative and qualitative data: it incorporates both numerical and descriptive information, allowing for a multi-faceted analysis of social risks and opportunities.
5. Integration with software: PSILCA is compatible with popular life cycle assessment software, such as openLCA, making it a practical tool for practitioners.

Applications:

- Corporate sustainability reporting: companies use PSILCA to evaluate and report on the social dimensions of their products' life cycles.
- Supply chain analysis: organizations can identify and mitigate social risks in their supply chains using PSILCA data.
- Policy development: researchers and policymakers can leverage PSILCA to design strategies for improving social conditions across industries.

4.2 Goal and scope

The social assessment using PSILCA aims to analyse the potential social impacts in the production process of BBFs, produced in Europe. The Functional Unit of the study is 1 tonne of BBFs. The products under assessment are the same as those under consideration in Deliverable 2.3 for LCA and LCC and follow the same identification code.

Therefore, the social assessment adopts the same structure as the LCA and LCC presented in Deliverable 2.3. It includes all the process needed to produce 1 USD dollar output of value created (2015) of the 13 BBFs. As the S-LCA using PSILCA follows the same structure as the LCA and LCC, the same system boundaries are used in this case. Therefore, a cradle-to-gate perspective is adopted, including all the materials, energy and infrastructure along upstream supply chain of the suppliers. For the background processes, homologue PSILCA sectors producing the inputs needed to produce BBFs are considered while for the foreground process, data inventory was obtained from the environmental and technological assessment and modelled in OpenLCA. In addition, the information obtained from the direct questionnaires sent to the companies analysed in Section 3 was adapted and used to complement the data needed for the S-LCA assessment. Risks assessment of social aspects was provided by PSILCA for the reference sector "Manufacture of Chemical products".

As social aspects are determined by socioeconomic context, as in PSILCA, social indicators are calculating based on country-specific data from EORA, we consider five scenarios where production can take place: Spain (ES), Belgium (BE), Sweden (SE), Italy (IT) and Poland (PL). They were chosen because they exemplify diverse socio-economic structures within Europe. These countries represent a balanced mix of geographic regions (Southern, Western, Northern, and Eastern Europe), economic development levels, labor market structures, and welfare state models. This diversity enables a comprehensive assessment of how social impacts may vary depending on the country of production. Social assessment for the foreground processes was conducted for each one of these countries, that is, considering the sectors from PSILCA for of each country. For example, the input flow "Water" was connected to the sector "Collection/ purification and distribution of water". Results show social impacts variations according to geographical distribution of productions processes.

4.3 Findings obtained using the PSILCA database

The results are presented by the 13 BBFs for the five countries considered. This multi-product and multi-regional perspective make it possible to identify the optimal scenarios for production, reducing social impacts and identifying the most affected categories.

Highest social impacts of products are distributed differently according to the countries (Table 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7). For Spain (ES), Belgium (BE), Sweden (SE) and Italy (IT), the category with the highest medium risk hours is "Fair Salary" For PL, the highest impact is found in in "Industrial water depletion". This category is also relatively significant for SW and BE, while it has a lower impact in ES and IT. This social impact is also relevant in comparison with other categories for SW and BE, while it is lower for ES and IT. The categories 'Trade Unionism' and 'Biomass Consumption' also show considerable number of medium risk hours across the countries and products.

Both "Fair Salary" and "Trade Unionism" correspond to the stakeholder category "workers" and, according to UNEP/SETAC definition, are evaluated through indicators measuring the wage distribution and freedom of association and collective bargaining. Categories "Industrial water depletion" and "Biomass consumption" are connected to the Local Community stakeholder group since affects negatively the access and use of the natural resources.

Other impact categories are observed repeatedly in the production of different BBFs, though only in specific countries, illustrating that identical production processes can result in varying social impacts depending on the geographical context. It is the case of "Corruption" or "Anti-competitive behavior or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation" that have more impact on ES, IT and PL than in BE and SE. On the contrary, categories "Migration Flow" and "Minerals consumption" concentrate more medium risk hours in comparison with other impact categories in SE and PL than in ES, IT and PL where the weight of these impacts are lower.

When looking at the specificities of each BBFs, social impacts vary depending on the composition of each product, as a result of the differing economic flow contributions of individual inputs. Products P9, P10 and P11 concentrate higher medium risk hours for all countries, corresponding to the ones with the highest cost of chemicals needed for the production of 1 tonne of product. Being P11, the one with the highest social impact profile and reflecting particularities of the productive process such as water consumption or biomass consumption apart from the other socioeconomic impact categories as Fair salary or Added Value.

Table 3. Social impact categories by Medium Risk Hours per tonne of the 13 BBFs in Spain

Impact category	PT1	PT2	PT3	PT4	PT5	PT6	PT7	PT8	PT9	PT10	PT11	PT12	PT13
corruption and bribery	29.10	17.86	20.56	17.10	18.43	56.70	31.98	28.00	559.49	554.39	987.85	59.12	173.31
anti-trust and monopoly legislation	9.47	2.39	4.08	2.14	3.08	50.03	3.70	1.12	88.68	85.83	570.21	28.81	103.53
Association and bargaining rights	8.05	1.58	3.12	1.26	2.19	1.43	2.33	1.10	82.38	79.70	487.27	24.75	15.55
Biomass consumption	131.59	42.97	64.13	38.60	50.77	212.46	71.18	48.79	1666.5	1629.5	6953.9	364.42	638.51
Certified environmental management system	9.82	2.33	4.12	2.01	3.03	30.46	3.50	1.31	95.94	92.88	586.51	29.73	62.93
Child Labour, female	13.76	3.79	6.17	3.51	4.76	107.03	5.94	1.34	117.66	113.92	780.07	39.27	88.58
Child Labour, male	25.49	6.02	10.66	5.29	7.90	113.44	9.24	2.74	234.71	227.07	1493.75	75.43	114.97
Child Labour, total	4.20	1.13	1.86	1.02	1.42	25.75	1.75	0.52	38.72	37.51	245.71	12.42	39.01
development	3.85	0.97	1.66	0.84	1.24	8.38	1.51	0.75	40.81	39.63	222.72	11.38	18.16
water pollution	1.23	0.39	0.59	0.36	0.47	11.48	0.62	0.16	10.60	10.29	65.98	3.33	6.20
Drinking water coverage	27.88	6.51	11.61	5.75	8.59	142.16	9.94	2.34	246.21	237.92	1637.25	82.41	122.28
Embodied agricultural area footprints	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.29	0.28	1.96	0.10	0.06
Embodied biodiversity footprints	0.62	0.13	0.25	0.11	0.18	1.38	0.19	0.06	5.93	5.73	37.88	1.91	3.95
Embodied forest area footprints	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.09	0.02	0.02	0.46	0.45	1.31	0.07	0.09
Embodied water footprints	0.06	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.02	0.01	0.61	0.59	3.67	0.19	0.46
Expenditures on education	0.38	0.10	0.17	0.09	0.13	1.42	0.16	0.07	3.86	3.75	21.38	1.09	1.65
Fair Salary	152.28	49.01	73.66	43.91	58.12	238.36	80.93	55.08	1914.15	1870.99	8097.6	423.77	737.73
Fatal accidents	0.05	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.14	0.02	0.01	0.53	0.51	3.12	0.16	0.37
Fossil fuel consumption	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.10	0.02	0.01	0.41	0.40	2.38	0.12	0.30
Frequency of forced labour	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.16	0.02	0.01	0.41	0.40	2.32	0.12	0.18
Gender wage gap	7.60	2.17	3.46	1.87	2.62	4.37	3.33	2.14	90.24	87.88	437.48	22.61	58.74
GHG Footprints	8.29	2.34	3.76	2.12	2.90	40.60	3.72	1.56	83.59	81.24	466.82	23.81	51.96
Goods produced by forced labour	0.24	0.07	0.11	0.06	0.08	0.42	0.11	0.07	2.81	2.75	12.91	0.67	0.92
Health expenditure	8.30	1.87	3.41	1.58	2.48	14.31	2.87	1.31	84.80	82.18	489.30	24.90	27.30
Illiteracy, female	24.06	5.57	9.98	4.90	7.37	117.89	8.47	2.02	213.14	205.95	1415.63	71.26	102.89
Illiteracy, male	14.36	2.91	5.64	2.42	4.02	38.00	4.29	1.20	132.71	128.10	871.45	43.92	53.81
Illiteracy, total	14.47	2.93	5.68	2.44	4.05	38.49	4.32	1.20	133.65	129.01	878.40	44.27	54.16
Indigenous rights	1.91	0.59	0.90	0.52	0.70	3.95	0.96	0.60	22.83	22.28	103.17	5.36	9.14
Industrial water depletion	16.76	3.26	6.48	2.61	4.54	14.26	4.72	1.83	164.61	159.03	1024.69	51.85	49.77
International migrant stock (site)	0.39	0.10	0.17	0.08	0.12	0.34	0.15	0.08	4.29	4.17	23.01	1.18	2.24
Life expectancy at birth	1.55	0.46	0.72	0.43	0.56	11.81	0.72	0.22	14.50	14.06	92.96	4.70	26.90
Men in the sectoral labour force	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.07	0.04	0.03	0.79	0.78	2.30	0.13	0.33
Migration flows	6.61	1.66	2.84	1.41	2.11	2.33	2.60	1.60	75.59	73.50	382.96	19.71	29.52
Minerals consumption	3.40	0.76	1.39	0.64	1.01	6.59	1.14	0.48	34.04	32.96	203.07	10.31	14.86
Net migration	0.73	0.30	0.40	0.28	0.34	0.41	0.52	0.43	11.12	10.94	34.08	1.85	3.97
Non-fatal accidents	16.89	12.32	13.41	12.05	12.67	13.72	23.77	22.74	403.03	400.99	385.34	27.25	69.96
Pollution	20.80	5.02	8.78	4.44	6.54	100.00	7.72	2.23	189.81	183.67	1207.83	60.98	83.88
Promoting social responsibility	27.46	7.58	12.32	6.58	9.33	38.17	11.88	7.05	312.80	304.49	1547.64	79.78	117.26
Public sector corruption	54.42	13.75	23.45	12.06	17.58	185.27	21.40	9.04	546.90	530.59	3141.34	159.88	256.17
Risk of conflicts	11.28	2.82	4.84	2.54	3.64	64.33	4.37	1.16	101.05	97.78	655.26	33.05	64.32
Safety measures	11.53	9.90	10.29	9.82	10.04	15.11	19.56	19.08	314.39	313.69	141.16	13.75	30.77
Sanitation coverage	7.90	1.74	3.21	1.48	2.31	25.76	2.51	0.67	72.36	69.86	479.15	24.14	43.79
Social security expenditures	12.96	2.51	5.00	2.05	3.52	21.18	3.69	1.22	123.36	119.12	789.46	39.86	35.87
Trade unionism	99.24	35.49	50.71	32.09	40.92	79.63	59.90	45.57	1369.27	1342.11	5035.16	267.61	476.85
Trafficking in persons	26.25	6.47	11.19	5.79	8.39	144.50	9.98	2.60	234.41	226.78	1521.73	76.72	123.67
Unemployment	7.44	3.07	4.12	2.82	3.42	4.33	5.29	4.33	113.78	111.85	360.00	19.51	59.87
Value added (total)	48.22	15.57	23.37	13.90	18.39	61.11	25.53	17.63	610.18	596.42	2566.80	134.41	228.84
regulations	18.45	5.57	8.64	4.93	6.73	18.59	9.16	6.25	228.66	223.28	997.91	52.05	72.24
Weekly hours of work per employee	2.54	0.56	1.03	0.47	0.75	5.78	0.85	0.33	25.01	24.21	151.00	7.66	8.75
Women in the sectoral labour force	16.62	13.22	14.03	13.07	13.51	29.94	25.89	24.76	420.36	418.98	280.10	22.67	41.62
Workers affected by natural disasters	1.35	0.26	0.52	0.21	0.37	0.99	0.38	0.15	13.31	12.86	82.22	4.16	2.73
Youth illiteracy, female	4.92	1.18	2.07	1.04	1.53	25.40	1.77	0.42	43.68	42.20	293.70	14.78	34.91
Youth illiteracy, male	2.42	0.62	1.05	0.55	0.79	13.82	0.95	0.26	21.65	20.95	138.69	7.00	10.57
Youth illiteracy, total	2.45	0.62	1.06	0.56	0.80	13.82	0.96	0.26	21.92	21.22	140.45	7.09	10.61

Table 4. Social impact categories by Medium Risk Hours per tonne of the 13 BBFs in Belgium

Impact category	PT1	PT2	PT3	PT4	PT5	PT6	PT7	PT8	PT9	PT10	PT11	PT12	PT13
Active involvement of enterprises in corruption and bribery	13.53	7.63	9.05	7.18	7.87	17.32	15.71	11.19	239.20	236.50	506.79	29.22	47.40
Anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation	4.66	1.02	1.88	0.86	1.37	11.90	1.53	0.56	45.19	43.71	280.43	14.20	24.05
Association and bargaining rights	10.53	2.25	4.23	1.83	3.00	5.32	3.27	1.55	108.24	104.78	632.26	32.14	27.86
Biomass consumption	91.13	25.79	41.39	22.34	31.37	80.89	40.23	25.26	1064.8	1037.2	5096.1	263.49	350.38
Certified environmental management system	10.32	2.75	4.56	2.34	3.35	17.11	3.92	1.88	107.27	104.08	594.45	30.34	32.21
Child Labour, female	3.26	0.82	1.40	0.68	1.01	4.43	1.13	0.51	33.09	32.06	192.09	9.77	11.14
Child Labour, male	16.07	3.62	6.59	2.96	4.70	8.69	5.19	2.50	166.00	160.78	954.84	48.60	37.13
Child Labour, total	3.18	1.01	1.53	0.86	1.14	2.72	1.40	0.81	35.86	34.89	177.50	9.15	12.10
Contribution of the sector to economic development	2.69	0.65	1.14	0.55	0.83	2.08	0.98	0.53	29.09	28.24	157.23	8.04	9.50
DALYs due to indoor and outdoor air and water pollution	0.31	0.16	0.20	0.14	0.15	0.29	0.20	0.13	3.91	3.84	14.48	0.77	0.56
Drinking water coverage	16.28	3.40	6.47	2.75	4.56	12.19	4.85	2.05	162.43	157.08	980.80	49.73	36.93
Embodied agricultural area footprints	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.00	0.18	0.17	1.14	0.06	0.03
Embodied biodiversity footprints	0.38	0.12	0.18	0.10	0.14	0.45	0.18	0.11	4.46	4.35	20.75	1.08	2.03
Embodied forest area footprints	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.45	0.45	0.58	0.04	0.03
Embodied water footprints	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.42	0.41	2.61	0.13	0.12
Expenditures on education	0.27	0.08	0.12	0.07	0.09	0.21	0.10	0.05	2.84	2.75	15.07	0.77	0.61
Fair Salary	180.24	55.92	85.61	49.28	66.50	135.36	90.19	62.37	2254.72	2201.88	9764.9	509.86	814.83
Fatal accidents	0.05	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.54	0.52	3.27	0.17	0.14
Fossil fuel consumption	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.14	0.01	0.00	0.33	0.32	1.96	0.10	0.09
Frequency of forced labour	0.07	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.89	0.87	3.64	0.19	0.16
Gender wage gap	2.47	0.62	1.07	0.52	0.77	1.46	0.89	0.47	26.47	25.67	145.60	7.44	10.54
GHG Footprints	4.23	1.31	2.00	1.15	1.55	5.00	2.10	1.39	51.62	50.39	227.53	11.85	13.53
Goods produced by forced labour	0.19	0.05	0.08	0.04	0.06	0.14	0.07	0.04	2.14	2.08	11.16	0.57	0.64
Health expenditure	8.70	2.34	3.86	1.95	2.80	4.17	3.22	1.72	93.18	90.43	501.66	25.67	19.36
Illiteracy, female	14.40	3.64	6.21	3.10	4.54	30.36	5.27	2.31	145.01	140.59	829.95	42.24	29.11
Illiteracy, male	12.79	3.16	5.46	2.69	4.00	27.86	4.65	2.02	128.59	124.66	738.43	37.57	25.77
Illiteracy, total	13.25	3.40	5.75	2.90	4.22	28.10	4.95	2.22	134.52	130.46	760.51	38.74	26.63
Indigenous rights	1.16	0.27	0.48	0.23	0.35	1.27	0.38	0.17	11.77	11.40	69.05	3.51	3.66
Industrial water depletion	87.26	29.84	43.55	26.74	34.71	52.11	49.70	37.24	1175.72	1151.14	4543.58	240.15	450.13
International migrant stock	7.30	2.12	3.35	1.84	2.56	4.94	3.33	2.18	87.30	85.10	405.55	21.03	30.62
International migrant workers (in the sector/site)	0.45	0.12	0.20	0.10	0.14	0.50	0.16	0.07	4.54	4.39	26.31	1.34	1.74
Life expectancy at birth	1.32	0.55	0.74	0.47	0.56	0.78	0.71	0.44	15.86	15.48	69.61	3.63	5.97
Men in the sectoral labour force	0.10	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.07	0.05	0.04	1.25	1.22	5.16	0.27	0.47
Migration flows	11.82	3.33	5.36	2.89	4.07	7.23	5.25	3.41	140.50	136.89	663.50	34.36	53.79
Minerals consumption	3.70	0.81	1.50	0.66	1.06	2.63	1.15	0.51	37.43	36.22	222.43	11.29	10.64
Net migration	0.41	0.15	0.21	0.14	0.17	0.28	0.25	0.19	5.69	5.58	20.64	1.10	2.24
Non-fatal accidents	1.45	0.85	0.99	0.79	0.85	1.11	1.38	1.18	25.32	25.02	54.88	3.15	5.62
Pollution	13.24	2.96	5.42	2.44	3.88	11.43	4.31	2.02	135.86	131.58	786.75	40.02	34.52
Promoting social responsibility	35.64	8.04	14.62	6.64	10.54	16.73	11.96	6.29	381.10	369.45	2146.41	109.49	187.97
Public sector corruption	34.07	7.99	14.22	6.65	10.23	46.70	11.43	5.01	343.50	332.64	2010.57	102.18	88.48
Risk of conflicts	7.09	1.56	2.88	1.28	2.04	8.51	2.18	0.86	69.75	67.44	427.26	21.64	21.99
Safety measures	7.54	5.76	6.19	5.62	5.83	9.67	10.87	10.26	179.58	178.76	157.69	11.47	20.55
Sanitation coverage	5.32	1.71	2.57	1.52	1.95	26.95	2.43	0.90	50.97	49.50	289.90	14.75	14.53
Social security expenditures	13.84	3.30	5.82	2.73	4.19	7.87	4.72	2.38	145.07	140.63	811.82	41.40	28.19
Trade unionism	36.19	8.24	14.91	6.73	10.62	20.14	11.63	5.50	371.93	360.14	2156.14	109.68	92.93
Trafficking in persons	15.85	3.43	6.39	2.81	4.54	17.37	4.91	2.06	157.91	152.76	950.42	48.20	42.20
Unemployment	0.83	0.20	0.35	0.16	0.25	0.41	0.28	0.14	8.73	8.46	50.26	2.56	5.41
Value added (total)	34.05	9.13	15.08	7.80	11.27	18.86	14.01	8.61	389.73	379.19	1930.25	99.49	105.32
Violations of employment laws and regulations	13.81	3.09	5.65	2.53	4.03	9.76	4.42	2.06	141.42	136.92	824.32	41.91	37.68
Weekly hours of work per employee	2.47	0.54	1.00	0.44	0.71	1.67	0.78	0.37	25.28	24.48	147.51	7.50	6.88
Women in the sectoral labour force	7.75	5.65	6.16	5.52	5.78	11.66	10.72	10.04	178.93	178.01	177.84	12.40	21.06
Workers affected by natural disasters	1.86	0.42	0.77	0.34	0.54	0.94	0.58	0.26	18.84	18.23	111.57	5.67	4.54
Youth illiteracy, female	3.40	1.28	1.79	1.18	1.42	25.28	1.90	0.74	32.88	32.06	171.52	8.78	7.84
Youth illiteracy, male	1.52	0.48	0.73	0.41	0.54	3.05	0.66	0.33	16.14	15.69	83.81	4.30	2.96
Youth illiteracy, total	1.96	0.72	1.01	0.62	0.76	3.27	0.96	0.54	21.90	21.34	103.97	5.38	3.76

Table 5. Social impact categories by Medium Risk Hours per tonne of the 13 BBFs in Sweden

Impact category	PT1	PT2	PT3	PT4	PT5	PT6	PT7	PT8	PT9	PT10	PT11	PT12	PT13
Active involvement of enterprises in corruption and bribery	12.38	9.01	9.83	8.62	8.90	19.71	15.71	14.08	260.27	258.56	330.44	21.41	35.52
Anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation	2.05	0.65	0.98	0.59	0.77	9.92	1.05	0.53	22.21	21.66	110.82	5.71	13.48
Association and bargaining rights	2.05	0.67	1.00	0.59	0.78	1.83	1.07	0.73	25.71	25.13	108.03	5.66	4.93
Biomass consumption	63.00	22.64	32.29	20.37	25.87	48.47	37.38	27.99	855.3	838.1	3193.9	169.42	245.85
Certified environmental management system	5.36	1.31	2.28	1.10	1.65	8.60	1.89	0.85	54.66	52.96	315.65	16.06	21.19
Child Labour, female	1.45	0.49	0.72	0.43	0.55	5.74	0.70	0.33	15.11	14.71	77.90	4.00	5.04
Child Labour, male	4.58	1.49	2.23	1.32	1.72	8.12	2.29	1.42	54.07	52.76	244.2	12.69	12.01
Child Labour, total	1.15	0.38	0.56	0.34	0.44	1.52	0.60	0.40	14.21	13.88	60.88	3.18	4.24
Contribution of the sector to economic development	2.47	0.65	1.09	0.56	0.81	1.78	1.02	0.62	28.21	27.45	139.79	7.20	8.23
DALYs due to indoor and outdoor air and water pollution	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.41	0.40	1.80	0.09	0.08
Drinking water coverage	6.61	1.94	3.05	1.68	2.31	10.68	2.92	1.68	74.16	72.19	366.66	18.90	21.05
Embodied agricultural area footprints	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.28	0.01	0.01
Embodied biodiversity footprints	0.11	0.04	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.13	0.06	0.04	1.39	1.36	5.67	0.30	0.58
Embodied forest area footprints	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.23	0.22	0.26	0.02	0.09
Embodied water footprints	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.14	0.14	0.70	0.04	0.04
Expenditures on education	0.09	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.12	0.04	0.02	1.02	1.00	4.97	0.26	0.28
Fair Salary	146.48	55.60	77.32	50.40	62.79	93.72	93.18	72.48	2077.1	2038.0	7229.4	386.71	615.2
Fatal accidents	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.16	0.15	0.61	0.03	0.04
Fossil fuel consumption	0.14	0.05	0.07	0.04	0.05	0.50	0.07	0.04	1.58	1.54	7.41	0.38	0.46
Frequency of forced labour	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.16	0.16	0.70	0.04	0.05
Gender wage gap	1.38	0.44	0.67	0.39	0.52	0.88	0.70	0.49	17.31	16.91	73.39	3.84	3.64
GHG Footprints	1.94	0.65	0.96	0.58	0.76	3.44	1.05	0.70	24.23	23.69	101.83	5.33	7.35
Goods produced by forced labour	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.05	0.03	1.06	1.04	4.08	0.22	0.29
Health expenditure	2.26	0.70	1.07	0.61	0.82	1.71	1.05	0.67	26.78	26.10	123.18	6.39	5.36
Illiteracy, female	3.19	1.01	1.53	0.88	1.17	5.89	1.51	0.88	36.30	35.38	172.09	8.90	7.46
Illiteracy, male	2.56	0.76	1.19	0.66	0.90	1.44	1.17	0.76	30.44	29.67	139.99	7.26	5.41
Illiteracy, total	2.58	0.77	1.20	0.66	0.91	1.45	1.18	0.77	30.66	29.89	140.87	7.31	5.44
Indigenous rights	0.85	0.29	0.43	0.26	0.34	0.67	0.47	0.34	11.15	10.91	44.37	2.34	3.09
Industrial water depletion	46.80	17.83	24.75	16.17	20.15	21.04	30.06	23.74	672.34	659.82	2303.5	123.46	202.22
International migrant stock	5.97	2.14	3.06	1.93	2.45	3.83	3.54	2.68	81.52	79.88	303.24	16.09	24.10
International migrant workers (in the sector/site)	0.28	0.09	0.14	0.08	0.10	0.13	0.13	0.09	3.35	3.27	15.16	0.79	0.75
Life expectancy at birth	0.11	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.09	0.05	0.03	1.22	1.19	6.15	0.32	0.31
Men in the sectoral labour force	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.65	0.64	2.16	0.12	0.19
Migration flows	38.80	15.78	21.28	14.45	17.60	18.64	27.00	21.93	582.88	572.90	#####	99.77	179.14
Minerals consumption	34.94	14.70	19.54	13.51	16.27	17.77	25.27	20.76	536.25	527.43	#####	88.73	169.91
Net migration	0.37	0.15	0.20	0.14	0.17	0.22	0.26	0.21	5.57	5.48	17.30	0.94	1.73
Non-fatal accidents	0.26	0.13	0.16	0.11	0.12	0.39	0.16	0.09	3.09	3.02	12.98	0.68	0.52
Pollution	3.92	1.27	1.90	1.11	1.46	7.49	1.91	1.14	45.18	44.06	210.20	10.89	10.23
Promoting social responsibility	25.61	7.17	11.58	6.10	8.60	13.92	10.52	6.31	291.53	283.53	1475.2	75.93	140.41
Public sector corruption	10.98	3.21	5.07	2.79	3.83	14.92	4.87	2.87	124.7	121.40	608.3	31.39	32.17
Risk of conflicts	3.52	0.88	1.51	0.75	1.11	5.47	1.31	0.66	37.06	35.96	204.56	10.45	13.47
Safety measures	7.85	6.55	6.86	6.47	6.64	7.10	12.84	12.53	209.10	208.52	111.20	9.96	16.93
Sanitation coverage	0.99	0.32	0.48	0.28	0.36	1.51	0.46	0.27	11.29	11.00	54.11	2.80	2.92
Social security expenditures	3.32	1.02	1.57	0.88	1.20	1.57	1.56	1.04	40.09	39.10	180.25	9.37	6.96
Trade unionism	15.66	4.29	7.00	3.66	5.23	8.26	6.51	4.00	179.28	174.47	881.1	45.44	39.20
Trafficking in persons	6.14	1.76	2.80	1.53	2.11	12.42	2.65	1.43	67.22	65.39	343.60	17.66	20.61
Unemployment	0.20	0.06	0.09	0.05	0.07	0.15	0.09	0.06	2.41	2.35	11.22	0.58	0.63
Value added (total)	19.90	6.39	9.62	5.62	7.45	14.06	10.05	6.90	247.86	242.08	1066.1	55.69	69.58
Violations of employment laws and regulations	7.89	2.54	3.82	2.25	2.96	10.74	3.97	2.58	95.45	93.18	420.52	21.91	22.08
Weekly hours of work per employee	1.38	0.43	0.65	0.37	0.51	1.03	0.68	0.47	17.13	16.73	74.42	3.88	4.55
Women in the sectoral labour force	7.12	6.47	6.63	6.42	6.49	9.93	12.71	12.42	200.96	200.65	64.31	7.57	16.64
Workers affected by natural disasters	0.75	0.22	0.35	0.19	0.26	0.33	0.33	0.21	8.87	8.64	41.61	2.15	1.48
Youth illiteracy, female	0.40	0.11	0.18	0.09	0.13	0.24	0.16	0.09	4.42	4.30	22.65	1.16	1.32
Youth illiteracy, male	0.26	0.08	0.13	0.07	0.10	0.13	0.13	0.08	3.19	3.11	14.17	0.74	0.56
Youth illiteracy, total	0.27	0.09	0.13	0.07	0.10	0.13	0.13	0.09	3.31	3.23	14.78	0.77	0.57

Table 6. Social impact categories by Medium Risk Hours per tonne of the 13 BBFs in Italy

Impact category	PT1	PT2	PT3	PT4	PT5	PT6	PT7	PT8	PT9	PT10	PT11	PT12	PT13
Active involvement of enterprises in corruption and bribery	15.09	9.08	10.52	8.65	9.31	39.43	15.81	13.31	273.89	271.18	536.82	31.43	88.18
Anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation	5.08	1.45	2.32	1.35	1.82	37.35	2.35	0.75	47.95	46.51	300.84	15.23	76.65
Association and bargaining rights	7.98	1.27	2.87	0.95	1.92	3.14	1.73	0.42	74.11	71.34	506.00	25.44	23.50
Biomass consumption system	104.66	29.87	47.72	26.23	36.51	177.65	47.42	28.53	1211.5	1180.1	5909.3	305.13	659.98
Child Labour, female	5.16	2.12	2.85	2.13	2.43	82.12	3.56	0.93	44.60	43.50	288.33	14.59	146.65
Child Labour, male	16.99	3.97	7.07	3.50	5.25	83.40	6.07	1.57	154.89	149.66	1037.6	52.27	173.35
Child Labour, total	2.50	0.69	1.12	0.64	0.87	17.15	1.10	0.33	23.26	22.54	148.51	7.51	34.27
Contribution of the sector to economic development	2.91	0.81	1.31	0.71	1.00	7.05	1.27	0.69	32.16	31.28	166.37	8.55	19.73
DALYs due to indoor and outdoor air and water pollution	0.38	0.17	0.22	0.17	0.19	5.58	0.29	0.11	3.76	3.68	19.69	1.01	8.88
Drinking water coverage	15.87	3.95	6.79	3.58	5.13	102.65	6.13	1.36	140.23	135.50	967.81	48.67	203.25
Embodied agricultural area footprints	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.11	0.01	0.00	0.31	0.30	2.17	0.11	0.18
Embodied biodiversity footprints	0.36	0.08	0.15	0.07	0.11	1.38	0.12	0.04	3.44	3.32	22.88	1.15	4.78
Embodied forest area footprints	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.23	0.23	0.47	0.03	0.11
Embodied water footprints	0.07	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.07	0.02	0.00	0.67	0.65	4.57	0.23	0.33
Expenditures on education	0.26	0.07	0.12	0.06	0.09	1.18	0.11	0.04	2.62	2.54	15.69	0.80	2.64
Fair Salary	175.68	54.38	83.35	48.18	64.82	241.20	87.59	57.80	2152.7	2101.3	9631.9	501.41	1071.4
Fatal accidents	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.14	0.02	0.01	0.46	0.45	1.89	0.10	0.34
Fossil fuel consumption	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.07	0.01	0.00	0.23	0.22	1.38	0.07	0.18
Frequency of forced labour	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.13	0.01	0.00	0.32	0.31	1.98	0.10	0.30
Gender wage gap	3.39	0.72	1.36	0.59	0.97	3.66	1.07	0.48	34.51	33.40	205.14	10.42	15.69
GHG Footprints	4.80	1.85	2.55	1.75	2.11	32.35	3.09	1.70	56.73	55.54	251.87	13.13	66.69
Goods produced by forced labour	0.18	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.05	0.30	0.06	0.03	1.87	1.81	10.52	0.54	0.95
Health expenditure	7.57	1.53	2.97	1.26	2.11	15.84	2.24	0.73	72.13	69.65	465.97	23.52	42.10
Illiteracy, female	13.17	3.32	5.67	3.02	4.30	88.21	5.15	1.11	115.75	111.85	802.01	40.33	171.47
Illiteracy, male	10.33	1.90	3.91	1.54	2.73	25.26	2.71	0.53	92.83	89.39	649.87	32.63	62.45
Illiteracy, total	10.45	1.92	3.95	1.56	2.75	25.40	2.74	0.53	93.89	90.41	657.53	33.02	62.83
Indigenous rights	1.03	0.21	0.40	0.17	0.29	2.66	0.30	0.08	9.56	9.23	63.68	3.21	6.88
Industrial water depletion	26.28	5.28	10.29	4.26	7.26	16.61	7.75	3.41	265.57	256.85	1599.7	81.15	89.73
International migrant stock sector/ site)	4.99	0.97	1.93	0.79	1.36	8.22	1.41	0.46	47.60	45.95	308.62	15.58	24.39
Life expectancy at birth	0.82	0.26	0.39	0.24	0.31	6.46	0.42	0.15	8.03	7.81	47.35	2.13	12.61
Men in the sectoral labour force	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.49	0.48	1.64	0.09	0.17
Migration flows	13.13	3.29	5.64	2.79	4.18	7.53	5.10	3.03	147.83	143.69	760.69	39.08	53.90
Minerals consumption	3.44	0.65	1.32	0.53	0.92	7.46	0.94	0.23	31.71	30.57	215.24	10.83	20.44
Net migration	0.12	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.08	0.05	0.03	1.32	1.28	6.60	0.34	0.49
Non-fatal accidents	1.36	0.29	0.55	0.24	0.39	0.55	0.43	0.21	14.11	13.66	82.29	4.19	5.14
Pollution	13.01	3.42	5.71	3.12	4.36	84.38	5.37	1.47	118.91	115.10	781.67	39.44	167.20
Promoting social responsibility	50.74	13.11	22.10	11.08	16.22	54.90	19.10	10.08	549.03	532.83	3016.2	154.22	358.99
Public sector corruption	82.34	26.59	39.90	23.86	31.38	176.75	43.10	27.72	1007.8	984.24	4485.7	233.67	620.54
Risk of conflicts	7.25	1.84	3.13	1.68	2.38	46.58	2.88	0.72	65.39	63.23	441.47	22.24	97.11
Safety measures	8.21	6.31	6.76	6.19	6.43	9.95	12.14	11.59	200.95	200.13	160.97	12.11	21.14
Sanitation coverage	6.25	1.18	2.39	0.97	1.67	16.21	1.67	0.31	55.98	53.90	394.91	19.82	44.21
Social security expenditures	11.09	1.89	4.09	1.49	2.79	16.41	2.65	0.55	100.76	96.99	699.80	35.15	47.35
Trade unionism	37.20	7.13	14.31	5.71	10.00	30.51	10.35	3.99	365.58	353.14	2288.5	115.77	133.82
Trafficking in persons	14.57	3.95	6.49	3.66	5.01	110.79	6.25	1.51	129.67	125.48	878.91	44.27	218.90
Unemployment	1.27	0.34	0.56	0.29	0.42	1.51	0.53	0.32	14.48	14.09	73.22	3.77	7.92
Value added (total) regulations	41.90	10.77	18.20	9.23	13.57	51.80	16.67	9.39	463.57	450.59	2415.7	123.98	186.43
Weekly hours of work per employee	6.03	1.68	2.72	1.45	2.05	8.25	2.57	1.49	68.42	66.56	347.79	17.90	41.77
Women in the sectoral labour force	8.18	6.23	6.69	6.15	6.39	22.29	12.08	11.25	195.50	194.71	167.66	12.30	39.55
Workers affected by natural disasters	1.58	0.24	0.56	0.18	0.37	0.45	0.32	0.06	14.45	13.90	100.58	5.05	3.50
Youth illiteracy, female	2.11	0.54	0.92	0.50	0.70	13.89	0.85	0.21	18.94	18.32	128.15	6.45	28.83
Youth illiteracy, male	1.34	0.33	0.57	0.30	0.43	7.09	0.51	0.15	12.38	11.98	80.42	4.06	13.36
Youth illiteracy, total	1.36	0.33	0.58	0.30	0.43	7.12	0.52	0.15	12.55	12.14	81.69	4.12	13.38

Table 7. Social impact categories by Medium Risk Hours per tonne of the 13 BBFs in Poland

Impact category	PT1	PT2	PT3	PT4	PT5	PT6	PT7	PT8	PT9	PT10	PT11	PT12	PT13
corruption and bribery	60.16	31.46	38.35	29.52	33.00	107.06	53.66	44.33	1010.9	997.50	2589.92	144.83	650.43
Anti-competitive behaviour or violation of anti-trust and monopoly legislation	22.98	6.15	10.16	5.55	7.79	113.08	9.67	3.81	236.31	229.03	1473.18	74.79	530.08
Association and bargaining rights	10.83	2.62	4.58	2.20	3.36	7.16	3.95	2.21	120.37	116.83	663.90	33.96	112.69
Biomass consumption	344.58	90.22	150.92	77.49	113.21	295.14	141.61	85.79	3943.1	3835.9	19855.8	1022.3	1847.0
system	49.19	12.51	21.27	10.77	15.77	110.51	18.71	8.86	521.66	505.79	3035.65	154.68	649.49
Child Labour, female	31.98	8.44	14.06	7.27	10.57	27.71	13.29	8.12	367.87	357.94	1840.20	94.81	178.26
Child Labour, male	12.87	2.84	5.23	2.35	3.76	13.92	4.21	1.94	131.78	127.63	767.1	39.01	39.74
Child Labour, total	5.21	1.40	2.31	1.22	1.74	8.54	2.18	1.22	57.92	56.33	297.52	15.29	26.13
development	6.42	1.54	2.71	1.29	1.98	4.36	2.34	1.29	70.14	68.10	378.88	19.39	30.47
and water pollution	0.11	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.04	0.07	0.05	0.03	1.25	1.22	6.32	0.33	0.30
Drinking water coverage	15.55	3.49	6.37	2.86	4.56	8.92	5.07	2.48	161.30	156.26	921.08	46.90	31.44
Embodied agricultural area footprints	0.15	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.00	1.37	1.31	9.82	0.49	0.21
Embodied biodiversity footprints	1.18	0.30	0.51	0.26	0.38	2.53	0.45	0.23	13.59	13.16	84.83	4.32	45.50
Embodied forest area footprints	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.29	0.29	1.29	0.07	0.04
Embodied water footprints	0.14	0.03	0.06	0.03	0.04	0.31	0.04	0.02	1.32	1.28	8.32	0.42	0.75
Expenditures on education	0.48	0.12	0.21	0.10	0.15	0.38	0.19	0.11	5.36	5.21	27.96	1.43	2.11
Fair Salary	141.07	37.22	62.01	31.89	46.42	108.17	57.88	35.09	1611.3	1567.5	8085.1	416.35	641.3
Fatal accidents	0.15	0.04	0.07	0.04	0.06	1.13	0.07	0.02	1.42	1.38	8.65	0.44	1.44
Fossil fuel consumption	0.05	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.12	0.02	0.01	0.58	0.56	3.13	0.16	0.29
Frequency of forced labour	0.06	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.09	0.02	0.01	0.60	0.59	3.22	0.16	0.28
Gender wage gap	6.28	1.71	2.80	1.49	2.12	11.59	2.67	1.51	70.89	68.93	370.07	19.01	63.77
GHG Footprints	26.88	6.73	11.54	5.73	8.57	21.55	10.46	6.10	301.03	292.56	1565.4	80.37	133.58
Goods produced by forced labour	0.41	0.10	0.18	0.09	0.13	0.42	0.16	0.09	4.56	4.43	23.71	1.22	2.03
Health expenditure	8.71	2.08	3.66	1.75	2.68	8.14	3.16	1.68	93.71	90.94	511.24	26.14	33.63
Illiteracy, female	6.40	1.13	2.39	0.87	1.63	1.46	1.56	0.53	61.38	59.20	396.03	19.98	8.74
Illiteracy, male	6.25	1.08	2.32	0.83	1.57	1.41	1.50	0.49	59.71	57.57	387.73	19.56	8.60
Illiteracy, total	6.29	1.09	2.33	0.84	1.58	1.21	1.51	0.51	60.16	58.01	389.67	19.66	8.51
Indigenous rights	1.59	0.44	0.71	0.39	0.54	6.61	0.68	0.28	16.01	15.54	90.84	4.63	10.34
Industrial water depletion	611.67	160.82	268.40	138.29	201.78	477.27	253.85	156.55	7063.4	6873.0	35242.6	1816.2	3463.8
International migrant stock	2.61	0.69	1.15	0.60	0.85	7.29	1.03	0.46	26.77	25.97	150.49	7.67	11.44
sector/ site)	0.47	0.15	0.23	0.14	0.18	0.70	0.24	0.16	5.76	5.62	25.02	1.31	2.27
Life expectancy at birth	0.60	0.20	0.29	0.18	0.23	5.19	0.31	0.09	5.47	5.31	33.24	1.68	5.62
Men in the sectoral labour force	0.37	0.11	0.17	0.09	0.13	0.31	0.16	0.10	4.40	4.29	21.19	1.10	2.27
Migration flows	35.96	9.62	15.90	8.28	11.98	25.95	15.16	9.48	418.07	406.93	2056.2	106.09	185.32
Minerals consumption	33.73	8.88	14.81	7.64	11.13	30.09	13.96	8.48	386.80	376.33	1941.9	100.01	185.00
Net migration	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.70	0.68	3.33	0.17	0.25
Non-fatal accidents	0.60	0.28	0.35	0.24	0.27	1.43	0.37	0.22	7.21	7.05	29.72	1.56	2.60
Pollution	12.67	3.21	5.47	2.74	4.05	13.81	4.92	2.73	138.85	134.90	729.71	37.42	43.07
Promoting social responsibility	146.29	41.35	66.43	35.74	50.02	182.23	62.61	36.89	1677.9	1632.3	8570.9	441.10	1370.3
Public sector corruption	64.49	16.63	28.05	14.31	20.92	102.34	25.62	13.80	702.2	682.28	3723.3	190.80	301.78
Risk of conflicts	16.56	4.42	7.32	3.91	5.52	64.01	6.79	2.82	165.78	160.89	951.19	48.42	93.01
Safety measures	29.13	20.82	22.81	20.33	21.45	27.60	39.96	37.96	680.21	676.51	703.78	48.50	131.46
Sanitation coverage	5.17	1.33	2.25	1.13	1.66	4.67	1.98	1.09	56.53	54.90	300.11	15.38	22.15
Social security expenditures	7.79	1.54	3.03	1.23	2.12	2.89	2.20	0.94	77.75	75.16	472.32	23.94	13.24
Trade unionism	317.81	83.04	139.07	71.23	104.32	221.51	130.69	80.61	3664.0	3564.8	18327.1	944.23	1729.7
Trafficking in persons	16.14	4.06	6.95	3.43	5.11	12.64	6.10	3.39	176.07	171.01	928.63	47.59	38.16
Unemployment	0.93	0.28	0.43	0.25	0.34	5.59	0.44	0.17	9.26	9.00	52.36	2.67	7.48
Value added (total)	96.42	27.86	44.23	24.42	33.99	97.01	44.86	29.36	1163.7	1134.6	5417.5	281.00	624.76
regulations	10.28	2.90	4.67	2.51	3.53	7.55	4.50	2.83	119.85	116.73	572.51	29.60	30.14
Weekly hours of work per employee	27.33	5.80	10.93	4.71	7.76	14.07	8.42	3.95	281.35	272.31	1660.27	84.37	116.64
Women in the sectoral labour force	37.68	22.83	26.38	22.21	24.22	83.74	43.35	39.01	768.79	762.02	1354.05	81.29	562.83
Workers affected by natural disasters	3.07	0.85	1.38	0.74	1.05	1.44	1.34	0.87	36.29	35.35	171.10	8.86	8.17
Youth illiteracy, female	0.71	0.14	0.28	0.11	0.19	0.24	0.19	0.07	6.91	6.67	43.59	2.20	1.12
Youth illiteracy, male	0.67	0.13	0.26	0.11	0.18	0.21	0.18	0.07	6.53	6.30	40.78	2.06	1.06
Youth illiteracy, total	0.67	0.13	0.26	0.11	0.18	0.21	0.18	0.07	6.56	6.34	41.04	2.08	1.07

5 Discussion and feedback on all examined BBFs

In this study, all analysed companies are engaged in the production and distribution of BBFs within their respective local regions, representing a practical application of CE principles. The data collected from the case studies suggest a generally high level of awareness regarding the social implications of their activities. The following sections provide an analysis of the social impacts associated with BBFs and their influence on various stakeholder groups.

5.1 Categories and subcategories of social impacts

The assessment uses predefined **categories** and **subcategories** of social impacts, aligned with UNEP guidelines, to ensure consistency and comprehensiveness in the analysis. The categories include impacts on: workers, local communities, consumers (farmers and end-users), suppliers, policy and regulatory bodies/government authorities.

Workers

- **Subcategories:** job satisfaction, occupational health and safety, fair wages.
- Impacts include creating local jobs and maintaining equitable working conditions for employees.

Discussion on examined BBFs: The companies involved in the production of BBFs demonstrate a generally positive approach to working conditions, emphasizing safety, training and professional development. However, the workforce in these companies is predominantly male, which may be attributed to the physically demanding nature of the work. Additionally, it was observed that male employees tend to receive slightly higher average monthly salaries. In general, the lowest salary levels are associated with a smaller proportion of employees, with the exception of the BBF3 case study, where the disparity between the average and the lowest salary is minimal.

All companies report offering some form of employee training, ranging from occupational safety to specialized programs such as sales or work-at-height training. These efforts indicate a commitment to employee development and operational efficiency. Health and safety protocols are in place across all companies. Examples include the identification and analysis of workplace hazards, adherence to recognized safety standards such as ISO 9001, and the involvement of ORP firms. Some companies report that these external firms perform monthly site inspections, which supports a safety improvement. Additionally, internal systems are used to report and monitor incidents and safety issues. These typically involve immediate communication of hazards, documentation of incidents, and structured follow-up actions to mitigate future risks. This suggests that companies not only comply with basic regulatory requirements but also invest in active safety management. Overall, the case studies reflect a responsible and proactive stance toward working conditions, emphasizing both compliance and continuous improvement in occupational health and safety.

Local communities

- **Subcategories:** access to resources, community health, local development.
- Positive impacts involve supporting local economies and addressing environmental concerns, while potential risks include odor or other nuisances from the production facility.

Discussion on examined BBFs: The companies examined in the case studies display varying levels of engagement with local communities, primarily through employment, improvement in regional supply chains, and indirect socio-economic benefits.

Companies highlight the local nature of their operations, noting the proximity of customers and suppliers. This regional focus not only supports local economies but also contributes to reduced operational costs by providing local resources, aligning with both environmental and social sustainability goals. For example, some companies report benefits such as reduced fertiliser costs for local farmers, which in turn improve agricultural profitability and foster positive relationships with stakeholders. Moreover, the companies contribute to the well-being of the local community by managing potentially hazardous waste materials and transforming them into value-added products, thereby supporting improvements in public health and environmental quality.

In terms of employment, the companies collectively provide local jobs, often offering full-time positions. Employment statistics suggest these companies contribute to local job markets, enhancing economic stability within their regions. The companies demonstrate engagement in the educational and cultural development of local communities through their active participation in related initiatives and activities. However, responses indicate limited engagement in formal assessments of social impacts on the local community. Most companies reported that they have not conducted formal assessments of their influence on local populations or stakeholder perceptions. This suggests that while the companies may generate tangible local benefits, their community engagement strategies are informal and not systematically evaluated.

Consumers (farmers and end-users)

- **Subcategories:** product quality, affordability, health, and safety.
- Benefits include improved soil fertility and plant health; potential risks involve contamination concerns.

Discussion on examined BBFs: The companies show varying levels of engagement and communication with their consumers, who are primarily farmers and agricultural businesses. Their relationships are largely shaped by transparency, product performance, and localized service delivery. A key strength of most companies is their proximity to consumers. This allows for direct communication and feedback, as well as more responsive product delivery and support. This closeness enhances trust and simplifies logistics, contributing to stronger

customer relationships. Some companies provide detailed product information, such as user guides or safety sheets, which are distributed with BBFs. This transparency reflects a commitment to responsible communication, helping end users understand both the benefits and safe usage of these products.

However, the depth of customer satisfaction assessment varies. While companies often refer to informal feedback from clients—especially regarding improved crop yield or reduced fertiliser costs—there is limited evidence of formal mechanisms like structured surveys or follow-up evaluations. One company explicitly stated that it does not conduct formal customer satisfaction assessments, suggesting that systematic user engagement is not yet standard practice across the sector.

In summary, the companies generally maintain positive relationships with their consumers through local accessibility and transparent product information. However, more formalized feedback and satisfaction monitoring systems could strengthen these relationships.

Suppliers

- **Subcategories:** business ethics, collaboration opportunities, and supply chain stability.
- Partnerships with suppliers can boost local businesses and ensure the ethical sourcing of materials.

Discussion on examined BBFs: The analyzed companies generally maintain stable and regionally focused relationships with their suppliers. Several companies emphasize local sourcing, which supports regional economies —aligning with both cost efficiency and environmental goals.

While cooperation with suppliers appears routine and functional, the companies do not report formalized sustainability criteria or partnership frameworks in supplier selection. Standards for cooperation are not extensively detailed, suggesting that supplier relationships are managed pragmatically, with limited strategic engagement.

Overall, supplier relations are based on practicality and proximity, but there is room for developing clearer sustainability or quality standards within the supply chain.

Policy and regulatory bodies / government authorities

- **Subcategories:** regulatory compliance, policy alignment.
- BBFs must align with environmental and agricultural policies to gain acceptance and avoid penalties.

Discussion on examined BBFs: The companies demonstrate general compliance with national and EU regulations, particularly regarding environmental standards, waste handling, and product safety. Interactions with authorities are mostly procedural focused on permits, inspections, and reporting requirements. In summary, while regulatory compliance is

consistently observed, more proactive engagement with policy development remains underutilized.

5.2 Stakeholder analysis

5.2.1. Main stakeholder groups

The life cycle of the examined BBFs involves a variety of stakeholders, each with unique interests, expectations, and roles in the production, distribution, and use of the product. The main stakeholder groups include:

1. Farmers and end-users

These are the primary users of all examined BBFs, including farmers, gardeners and agricultural companies. Their key interests are improving soil quality, increasing crop yields, and reducing dependency on chemical fertilisers.

2. Local communities

Residents living near the BBFs' processing facilities in areas where BBFs are applied. They are concerned about potential environmental impacts, public health issues, and the benefits of job creation.

3. Employees

Workers directly involved in the production process, such as machine operators, laboratory staff, drivers and technical personnel responsible for the production of BBFs.

4. Suppliers

Companies provide raw materials, such as biobased waste materials, packaging materials, chemicals used in the treatment processes, and energy. The quality of their services and adherence to social and environmental standards affect the overall perception of BBFs.

5. Government authorities and regulatory institutions

Local governments, environmental inspection agencies, and regulatory bodies monitor compliance with laws regarding environmental protection, public health, workplace safety, and social norms.

6. Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and social organisations

Groups focused on environmental protection, public health, and sustainable development. They may evaluate the product's impact and engage in public discussions about its benefits and risks.

Table 8. Characteristics of stakeholder groups

Stakeholder Group	Key Needs and Expectations	Concerns and Challenges
Farmers and End-Users	Improved soil quality, higher yields, lower costs	Product safety, consistent quality
Local Communities	Job creation, reduced odors, health protection	Environmental and transport-related impacts
Employees	Safe working conditions, job stability	Risk of exposure to harmful substances
Suppliers	Stable orders, clear quality standards	Compliance with environmental regulations
Government Authorities	Compliance with laws, transparent reporting	Enforcement of strict standards
NGOs and Social Organisations	Sustainable practices, minimal environmental impact	Lack of transparency, potential risks

5.2.2. Main stakeholder groups interests and expectations

Each stakeholder group has unique needs and expectations related to the BBFs life cycle.

1. Farmers and end-users

Interests: Improving agricultural productivity while lowering costs.

Expectations:

- availability of BBFs in local markets,
- assurance of quality and safe application.

Needs: Education and guidelines for product usage to maximize benefits and avoid misuse.

2. Local communities

Interests: Economic development through local employment and reduced nuisances such as odor emissions.

Expectations: Regular communication from BBFs producers regarding plant operations and community engagement initiatives.

3. Employees

Interests: A safe and stable working environment.

Expectations: Access to training programs, protective equipment, and competitive salaries.

Needs: Compliance with workplace safety standards and regular risk assessments.

4. Suppliers

Interests: Long-term contracts and partnerships with BBFs suppliers.

Expectations: Clear technical requirements for raw materials and streamlined logistics processes.

5. Government authorities and regulatory institutions

Interests: Monitoring and ensuring compliance with relevant laws.

Expectations: Transparent reporting and cooperation during audits.

Needs: Accurate data on environmental and social impacts.

6. NGOs and social organisations

Interests: Advocating for sustainable practices and public awareness.

Expectations: Engagement in dialogue with BBFs producers regarding the ecological and social aspects of the BBFs.

5.2.3. Impact of the BBFs product system on stakeholders

The production and distribution of BBFs have both positive and potentially negative impacts on stakeholders. Analyzing these impacts helps identify areas requiring optimization.

Table 9. Stakeholder impact analysis of BBFs and distribution

Stakeholders	Positive impacts	Potential risks
Farmers and end-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improved soil fertility and crop productivity, reduced dependence on expensive chemical fertilisers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> insufficient education about the safe use of products derived from sewage sludge.
Local communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> creation of jobs within the local area at the production site, logistics and distribution, environmental improvement through sustainable waste reuse. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> odor emissions and potential concerns about transport routes.
Employees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> skill development through training programs, stable employment opportunities in the growing sector of BBFs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> potential health hazards related to handling treated biobased waste materials
Suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> opportunity for collaboration in a sustainable supply chain. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> pressure to meet stringent quality and environmental requirements.
Government authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> achievement of environmental and waste management goals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> necessity to allocate resources for stricter enforcement and oversight.

NGOs and social organisations

- collaboration opportunities to promote sustainable practices.
- conflicts over differing perspectives on the risks of using sewage sludge

5.3 Discussion on PSILCA findings

The results demonstrate that the geographical context of production influences social sustainability of BBFs. Social impacts derived from the production of BBFs are not only dependent on the company's behavior or the production processes but also on the nature of trade relations between countries and monetary flows which determines suppliers' characteristics. The double comparison, across countries and across products, reveals how social impacts are distributed differently, shedding light on the need to consider a country's economic structure as a key determinant of social sustainability.

Among the social impacts identified, the access to natural resources for local communities and the working conditions (including fair salary and freedom of association) emerge as critical social aspects within the value chain of BBFs. Therefore, it becomes necessary to develop socially responsible supply chains.

The implementation of this specific analysis complements the company-level assessment by providing an overview of the most affected social categories throughout the product's life cycle. **The use of the PSILCA database highlights the importance of assessing social impacts along the supply chain, enabling the identification of optimal scenarios and evaluating overall product performance and allows the optimisation of social benchmarking complementing other approaches.**

Further research is needed that incorporates additional Functional Units, such as nutrient levels, to better understand how social impacts are distributed and how they relate to product functionality. Including this type of data could provide a more nuanced view of the results and improve the relevance of the findings for decision-making.

5.4 Summary of key findings

This S-LCA has provided a comprehensive evaluation of the social performance of BBFs developed under the Novafert project. The findings confirm that BBFs, derived from organic waste materials, can offer considerable social and environmental benefits.

These benefits are especially evident in terms of:

- **job creation** in local communities and rural regions,
- **improved working conditions** and safety protocols in most production sites,

- **promotion of CE practices**, through waste valorisation,
- **environmental and public health improvements**, due to reduced chemical fertiliser use.

The analysis also reveals areas where improvement is necessary. These include:

- more structured stakeholder engagement,
- greater transparency in customer and community relations,
- limited gender representation in the workforce,
- insufficient monitoring of social responsibility along the supply chain,
- social impacts are highly dependent on the geographic context, where production takes place.

In summary:

- all case studies demonstrated basic compliance with legal requirements and a commitment to social responsibility,
- health and safety measures are generally effective, with no major incidents reported,
- there is limited formal monitoring of social impacts on local communities,
- supplier selection and evaluation practices often lack explicit social criteria,
- customer feedback mechanisms are informal or non-existent,
- disparities in salary levels and gender distribution were observed across several cases.

5.5 Recommendations

In light of the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to strengthen the social sustainability of BBF value chains. These actions are designed to enhance stakeholder relationships, improve working conditions, and ensure compliance with evolving expectations in the field of sustainable production.

Promote inclusive and equitable working environments

It is recommended that companies develop and implement formal policies to support workplace diversity, inclusion, and non-discrimination. Attention should be given to closing gender pay gaps and encouraging the participation of women and underrepresented groups in technical and decision-making roles.

Strengthen occupational health and safety practices

While general safety measures are in place, ongoing investment in employee training and preventive safety measures is essential. Regular internal audits, updated risk assessments, and continuous improvement protocols are recommended to maintain a high standard of occupational safety.

Enhance community engagement and impact monitoring

Companies should conduct formal assessments of their social and environmental impacts on local communities. In addition, community outreach efforts—such as open dialogue sessions, public consultations, and educational campaigns—can help build trust and long-term acceptance of BBFs.

Establish customer feedback and satisfaction monitoring

The implementation of systematic customer satisfaction monitoring tools, such as surveys and feedback forms, is recommended. These mechanisms will enable producers to assess product performance from the user's perspective and respond to market needs more effectively.

Develop supplier evaluation standards for social responsibility

Companies are encouraged to introduce clear standards for social responsibility in their supplier selection processes. This may include codes of conduct, ethical sourcing requirements, and regular self-assessments or audits of supplier practices related to labour rights and environmental performance.

Improve transparency and stakeholder communication

Transparency in reporting and active stakeholder communication should be integrated into company practices. Regular publication of compliance records, health and safety statistics, and social performance indicators will enhance credibility and support policy alignment.

Promote responsible social sustainability measures through supply chain

Support suppliers in BBF value chain to adopt fair labor practices, ensure safe working conditions, and engage in community development initiatives to foster social sustainability along the life cycle of the product, reducing negative social impacts.

5.6 Future challenges

To ensure long-term viability and continued social and environmental performance, BBF producers must be prepared to address several future challenges. These challenges reflect both sector-specific trends and broader shifts in regulatory, technological, and societal expectations, such as:

- **technological advancements:** continuous investment in research and development is necessary to improve the efficiency of BBF production processes, including sludge dewatering and nutrient recovery technologies. Innovation will be key to maintaining competitiveness and environmental integrity,
- **regulatory compliance:** the regulatory landscape for waste-derived products is evolving. Companies must anticipate and adapt to changes in EU and national legislation related to environmental protection, fertiliser safety and CE mandates,

- **market competitiveness:** the biobased fertiliser market grows; companies must clearly demonstrate the economic and agronomic value of BBFs. Competitive pricing, consistent product quality, and measurable sustainability benefits will be critical for market growth,
- **public perception:** overcoming public concerns about fertilisers derived from sewage sludge or other waste materials remains a challenge. Transparent communication, stakeholder education, and scientific evidence are essential to fostering trust and wider acceptance,
- **stakeholder collaboration:** collaborative efforts involving public authorities, agricultural organisations, research institutions, and civil society actors will be necessary to support scaling up production, establishing best practices, and ensuring regulatory compliance,
- **alignment with global sustainability goals:** aligning BBF development with international sustainability frameworks, such as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), can enhance the visibility, funding opportunities, and societal relevance of these products,
- **fostering sustainable and socially responsible supply chains of BBF:** promoting responsible actions and the participation of suppliers in community social programs, as well as strengthening worker protection measures, thereby improving the social impact and sustainability throughout the product's life cycle.

Addressing these challenges will require a proactive approach, fostering innovation, collaboration, and adaptability to ensure the long-term viability and societal benefits of BBFs.

References

- Bouillass, Ghada, Isabelle Blanc, and Paula Perez-Lopez. 2021. "Step-by-Step Social Life Cycle Assessment Framework: A Participatory Approach for the Identification and Prioritization of Impact Subcategories Applied to Mobility Scenarios." *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 26(12): 2408–35. <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s11367-021-01988-w>.
- Ciroth, A., and Eisfeldt, F. 2015. *A New Comprehensive Database for Social LCA: PSILCA*. New Delhi.
- European Parliament. 2009. "Regulation 1221/2009 on the Voluntary Participation by Organisations in a Community Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS)." *Official Journal of the European Union* 1221(342): 1–45. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009R1221&qid=1417544679944&from=EN>.
- ISO 14001. 2015. *Environmental Management Systems — Requirements with Guidance for Use*. International Organization for Standardization.
- ISO 14040. 2006. *Environmental Management — Life Cycle Assessment — Principles and Framework*. International Organization for Standardization.
- ISO 9001. 2015. *Quality Management Systems — Requirements*. International Organization for Standardization.
- Jørgensen, A., Le Bocq, Liudmila, A. Nazarkina, L., Hauschild, M. 2008. "Methodologies for Social Life Cycle Assessment." *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 13(2): 96–103. <http://link.springer.com/10.1065/lca2007.11.367>.
- Maister, K., Di Noi, C., Ciroth, A., Srocka, M. 2020. *PSILCA v.3 Database Documentation*.
- UNEP/SETAC. 2009. Benoît, C., Mazijn, B. (Eds.) *Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products*. UNEP/SETAC Life Cycle Initiative.
- UNEP. 2020. Benoît Norris, C., Traverso, M., Neugebauer, S., Ekener, E., Schaubroeck, T., Russo Garrido, S., Berger, M., Valdivia, S., Lehmann, A., Finkbeiner, M., Arcese, G. (eds.) *Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations 2020*. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP).

D2.5 – Results of social LCA

Annex 1: Survey template used for data collection

Novafert

T.2.6 social LCA

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this questionnaire is to collect the information necessary to carry out a Social Life Cycle Analysis (S-LCA) for the product X, in accordance with the UNEP/SETAC guidelines. This analysis takes into account the social impact and working conditions at all stages of the product life cycle: from the sourcing of raw materials, through production, transport, use, to

Company:
Country:
Data:
Company's representative position completing the questionnaire:
Product:
Product description:
Annual production:

the end of the product's life – disposal/reuse.

Please answer the following questions in accordance with available data and company practices.

COMPANY PROFILE

1. Production

1.1. Please briefly describe the production activities of your company (e.g.. water supply network management, wastewater treatment, etc.):

- _____
- _____

1.2. What are the main markets (geographical and sectoral) targeted by your company Please indicate the economic importance from your overall sales in %:

- Ej. Germany, agriculture (40%)
- _____ (___ %)
- _____ (___ %)

1.3. What was the company's gross annual economic output last year (2024 if possible, 2023 if 2024 results are not consolidated yet?

1.4. What are the anticipated social benefits of using a BBFs (e. g. Proximity to suppliers, reduction of exposition to chemical products)?

SPECIFIC QUESTIONS - STAKEHOLDERS

EMPLOYEES

2. Working conditions

2.1. How many people did the company employ during the last year? (Please indicate the number of employees in the following categories):

- Total: _____ (___ % women)
- Full-time: _____ (___ % women)
- Temporary: _____ (___ % women)
- Part-time: _____ (___ % women)

2.2. What is the average salary in the company?

- Total: _____
- For women: _____
- For men: _____

2.3. What is the minimum salary in the company? What percentage of employees have it?

- Total: _____ (_____ %).

2.4. What are the key steps in the production process (e.g., sludge dewatering, composting, packaging) and how many workers are involved?

Production process	N° Workers involved
Eg. Administrative tasks	3 (full-time), 2 (part-time)

2.5. What is the standard working hours for employees per week?

2.6. Is overtime common? Yes No

- If yes, please, indicate the number of extra hours per week: _____ and how often it is: _____

2.7. Does the company offer training and professional development opportunities for employees?

Yes No

- If yes, please, indicate which ones: _____

2.8. What percentage of the company's budget is spent on employees' benefits (health care, training, etc.)?

3. Health and safety at work

3.1. What safety procedures are implemented in the workplace?

3.2. Is there a system for reporting and monitoring accidents and incidents related to workplace safety? Yes No

- If yes, please, indicate which one: _____

3.3. What are the accident rates for employees in the last 3 years?

- Total accidents at work: _____
- Fatal accidents: _____

4. Respecting workers' rights

4.1. What are the company's mechanisms for including employees' demands?

4.2. Is there union representation in the company? How is dialogue with union representatives organised?

4.3. Does the company carry out employees' satisfaction surveys?

- Are they publicly accessible? Yes No Where? _____

4.4. Does the company have a specific policy to promote equal treatment and prevent discrimination in the workplace? If so, please specify which ones:

- Equality Plan Yes No
- Protocol for prevention and action against harassment Yes No
- Existence of internal working committees responsible for that issue Yes No
- Formalisation and awareness training for staff on workplace harassment, sexual harassment, and harassment based on gender Yes No
- Please explain how this training is delivered:

- _____
- Code of Conduct Yes No

- Other initiatives carried out in the company:

CUSTOMERS/END USERS

5. User Health and Safety

5.1. Does the company conduct health safety studies on the product before it is placed on the market?

5.2. Does the company provide complete information about the composition and properties of the product, including potential hazards? Yes No

- Where is it available?

6. Customer satisfaction

7. Does the company regularly conduct customer satisfaction surveys or monitor customer feedback? Yes No

- How?

7.1. What are the customer satisfaction rates with the product

- Number of formal complaints: _____
- Number of positive reviews (please, indicate where the reviews are made)

SUPPLIERS

7. Rules of cooperation with suppliers

7.1. Which criteria do you follow to select suppliers of materials and services used in the production of BBFs?

7.2. Does the company have a policy of evaluating suppliers in terms of compliance with labour law and social standards? Yes No

- Which one? _____

8. Monitoring of Supplier Social Responsibility

8.1. Does the company conduct supplier audits to assess their social practices? Yes No

8.2. Does the company work with suppliers to improve working conditions and respect human rights? Yes No

- Please, indicate how: _____

LOCAL COMMUNITIES

9. Impact on the local community

9.1. Does the company have assessed the social impact on local community of the company?

Yes No

9.2. What are the potential benefits of BBFs production for the local community?

9.3. And the negative effects?

10. Social commitment

10.1. Does the company participate in social programs or initiatives aimed at supporting local communities? Yes No

- In which ones?

10.2. Does the company have any educational or information programs on sustainability and environmental protection? Yes No

- Which ones?

GOVERNMENT AUTHORITIES AND INSTITUTIONS

11. Regulatory compliance

11.1. Does the company comply with all local, national and international regulations regarding waste management and environmental protection (e.g. ISO 14001)? Yes No

- Please, indicate which ones:

11.2. Does the company take additional measures to improve its sustainability practices beyond what is required by law?

- Please, indicate how:

CONCLUDING REMARKS

12. Challenges & opportunities

12.1. What are the main challenges the company faces in the context of sustainability and social responsibility?

- And the opportunities?

13. Additional comments or suggestions

13.1. Is there any additional information the company would like to add about its approach to social responsibility or the social impact associated with the production of BBFs?

THANK YOU FOR COMPLETING THE QUESTIONNAIRE!